

REGARDING THE INTERPRETATION OF WORD FORMATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LINGUISTICS

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Abstract:

This article describes about some similarities and differences regarding the interpretation of word formation in English and Uzbek languages. Additionally, there are some analyzes of them.

Key words: affixation, abbreviation, composition, lexical way.

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The word is the most important nominative unit of the language, because it names things in existence, abstract concepts imagined as objects, motion-state, color-color, taste-taste, size-quantity, and character-properties. [2.140] When we read the lyceum textbooks, it says about the formation of words: New words are formed in two ways: 1. Based on the internal potential of each language. 2. Based on borrowing words from other languages. So, the branch of linguistics that studies the creation of a new word by adding certain building blocks to a word that already exists in the language is called word formation. [3. 135]

There are different attitudes and approaches in different literature and manuals about the formation of words in the Uzbek language. In particular, A. Gulomov distinguishes 5 ways of word formation:

- 1) Morphologically (affixation);
- 2) Syntactically (reduplication, composition, abbreviation);
- 3) Lexical way (making a word from one category by transferring it to another category);
- 4) In a semantic way;
- 5) Making phonetically (making by internal changes). [1.112]

Most of the literature on word formation in the Uzbek language considers the above five ways of word formation.

In all of the above methods, a new word is created. But there is another side of the matter. That is, different processes are understood and explained under the concept of word formation in different literatures. In particular, Sh. Shoabdurahmanov brought up the idea that "Word formation, no matter how it is, means creating a new word, like work+er=worker, "[5.167] Therefore, the new meaning and form created in any way in the language is the object of study of the phenomenon of word formation. Sh. Shoabdurahmanov's thoughts are in some sense consistent with the thoughts of the English linguist H. Marchand, "Word formation is a scientific field of language that studies examples of new lexical form parts (words) in the language. Word formation is in style and semantics A simple word is an unanalyzed, unmarked, lexical meaning do-er, un-do, rain-bow are related to word formation, but do, rain, bow are not." [7.111] In addition to the examples given above, we can

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see a similar idea in another literature: Word formation is the process of creating new words using stylistic and semantic forms and patterns in the language. For example, if we take the word "driver" in English, "verb+er" is used to form a personal noun from the verb driver+er. [6.135]

However, another guide to this direction, "Current Uzbek Literary Language", gives a different interpretation of this phenomenon. It is said that "making a word does not mean creating a new word in any way". He explains it using the Word [Entrepreneur]. Let's say the word [Entrepreneur] acquires a new meaning. However, there is no new word here. Therefore, it is necessary to distinguish between the phenomenon of artificial word formation and the phenomenon of lexemization of words that have acquired a new meaning. [4.143-144]

Judging from the above points, it can be seen that there are still many undiscovered aspects of word formation. Therefore, the goal of young people is to conduct deeper research on word formation, make a wider observation about it, eliminate the existing shortcomings, and clarify every detail of word formation in Uzbek with the help of clear evidence and examples.

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